

Contribution to the study of fungi associated with *Cistus ladanifer* in the north-east of Portugal

Miguel Torrejón

La Estrella, 18-1. E-12410 Altura, Spain (e-mail: m.torrejón@terra.es)

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Abstract. This report deals with 25 species and 4 varieties of fungi; which were collected in the north-east of Portugal. All of them were associated with *Cistus ladanifer* except *Terfezia olbiensis*, which was associated with *Cistus ladanifer* × *Cistus salviifolius*. Significant diagnostic characters are given for some of the collected specimens. Several species are of special interest: *Amanita muscaria* var. *inzengae*, *Cortinarius asiduus* var. *pleciocistus*, *Cortinarius cystidifer* and *Terfezia olbiensis*.

Key words: *Cistus ladanifer*, fungi, Portugal, taxonomy

Introduction

As a contribution to the inventory of the Portuguese mycota, this survey was carried out during the 14th Mycological Conference of the European Confederation of Mediterranean Mycology (C.E.M.M.) that was held in Bragança, in the north-east of Portugal, in November 2006.

As a part of this event, five forays took place in which the author collected 25 species and 4 varieties of fungi associated with *Cistus ladanifer*; only one, *Terfezia olbiensis*, was associated with *Cistus ladanifer* × *Cistus salviifolius*.

Methods

Some photographs, a few pen drawings and several descriptions of the main macroscopical characteristics were written down locally from fresh fungi. All collected fungi were dried and each collection halved and put into two different envelopes; one was deposited in the organization's herbarium and the other one is in the author's herbarium (MTH).

In the laboratory, dried fungi were rehydrated with the help of sodium hydroxide at 5 percent. Herbarium specimens have been studied in distilled water under a light microscope (40-1000×). Melzer's reagent and Congo red colorant were used when it was necessary.

The localities in the taxonomy part have been numbered and referred to as follows:

Site 1: Monte Morais, location 29TPF6845, 650-730 m, date of collection, 6 Nov 2006.

Site 2: Monte Morais, location 29TPF6845, 650-730 m, date of collection, 7 Nov 2006.

Site 3: Centro Hípico, location 29TPG6846, 650-700 m, date of collection, 9 Nov 2006.

Site 4: Serra de Montesinho, location 29TPH6846, 1 000 m, date of collection, 10 Nov 2006.

Species have been systematically arranged according to Kirk *et al.* (2001).

Taxonomy

Anamorphic fungi

Capnophialophora state of *Metacapnodium* sp.

Site 3. MTH 780. On leaves and branches of *Cistus ladanifer*.

This sooty mould forms spongy and pulvinate colonies, at first fulvous and finally black, covering large areas or the totality of some shrubs.

Hypomyces chrysospermus Tul. & C. Tul.

Site 2. MTH 792. On rotten *Leccinum corsicum* beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

AscomycotaOrder *Pezizales**Terfezia olbiensis* Tul.

Site 4. MTH 779. Hypogeous, 50 mm depth, beneath *Cistus ladanifer* × *Cistus salvifolius*.

Macromorphological features: Ascocarps subglobose 13-18 × 9-13 mm, breakable. Peridium slightly tomentose, cinnamon and plenty of small sandy particles. Gleba fleshy and compact, at first greyish white, then pinkish grey, brownish cream at maturity and finally brownish black, marbled with white-salmon veins dividing fleshy and compact areas.

Micromorphological features: Asci 59-70 × 49-62 µm, from subglobose to ovoid, sometimes with a small hyaline appendage 4-9 µm in length. Spores subspherical, 14-18 µm, pale yellow, sometimes with a large guttule inside, with verrucose ornamentation 1.5-2 µm in length.

BasidiomycotaOrder *Agaricales**Amanita muscaria* (L.) Lam. var. *inzengae* Neville & Poumarat

Site 3. MTH 790. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

The habitat and the greyish universal veil are two of the most important distinctive characteristics of this variety. The complete information about this variety can be found in Neville & Poumarat (2001).

Clitocybe agrestis Harmaja

Site 2. MTH 798. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Only two basidiocarps.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 22-24 mm in diameter, slightly viscid, flattened, hygrophanous, translucently striate, dark cream at the central area and light cream at the border. Lamellae from adnate to decurrent, white-cream, lamellulae present. Stipe 33-42 × 3 mm, cylindrical, concolorous with pileus but a little less coloured.

Micromorphological features: Basidia 18-24 × 5-5.5 µm, clavate, 4-spored, cheilocystidia absent. Basidiospores 4.5-5.3 × 3-3.5 µm, ellipsoid, smooth and hyaline.

Clitocybe cistophila Bon & Contu

Site 1. MTH 770. Site 2. MTH 775. Scattered, on loose leaf litter, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 17-36 mm in diameter, at first convex, then depressed at maturity, with involute margin, cream, hygrophanous, drying light-brown. Lamellae decurrent, white-cream. Stipe 23-48 × 3-5 mm, cylindrical, sinuous and concolorous with pileus. With characteristic aniseed smell.

Micromorphological features: Basidia 21-26 × 5-6 µm, clavate, hyaline with small oil droplets, 4-spored. Basidiospores 4-6 × 2.5-3.5 µm, ellipsoid, sometimes pyriform, hyaline with small oil droplets.

Clitocybe font-queri R. Heim

Site 2. MTH 776. Scattered, on loose leaf litter, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 12-22 mm in diameter, at first convex, later infundibuliform, grey, brownish grey in the center, velvety, with stretch marks at maturity. Lamellae decurrent, white, slightly serrated. Stipe 12-23 × 1.5-3 mm, cylindrical, curved and concolorous with pileus. With characteristic floury smell.

Micromorphological features: Pileipellis trichoderm with clavate to strangulated ending hyphae 4-8 µm wide.

Clitocybe vibecina (Fr.) Quél.

Site 3. MTH 782. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 17-52 mm in diameter, convex to depressed at maturity, hygrophanous, striated at the margin, brownish cream turning whitish cream when dry. Lamellae decurrent, cream greyish. Stipe 46-63 × 3-6 mm, cylindrical, sinuous, attenuated at the apex and broadened at the basal part.

Micromorphological features: Basidiospores 5-6 × 3-3.5 µm, ellipsoid, hyaline with small oil droplets.

Cortinarius assiduus Mahiques, A. Ortega & Bidaud var. *pleiocistus* A. Ortega, Vila & Bidaud

Site 2. MTH 789. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 17-34 mm in diameter, hygrophanous, convex, expanded at maturity, smooth, brown, sienna in the central area, slightly to obtusely mammiform. Abundant universal greyish white veil with persistent areas at maturity. Lamellae adnate, cinnamon with lilac tinges. Stipe 38-54 × 9-18 mm, cylindrical, white, with lilac tinges at the apex, broadened at the basal part, becoming hollow at maturity. Cortina persistent and tinged sienna by spores.

Micromorphological features: Basidia 34-41 × 8-11 µm, clavate, 4-spored. Basidiospores 8-10 × 6-8 µm, ellipsoid, slightly verrucose, brown, many of them with a big droplet.

In spite of longer basidia, the other measures are similar to the description of this new variety in Ortega *et al.* (2007).

Cortinarius cystidifer (Velen.) Reumaux (= *Hydrocybe cystidifera* Velen.)

Site 1. MTH 802. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Small collection.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 4-6 mm in diameter, convex, yellowish veil at the margin, mammiform, from snuff brown to cigar brown at the mammiform area. Lamellae distant. Stipe 11-17 × 1-1.5 mm, cylindrical, curved, floccose, covered with yellowish velar remnants.

Micromorphological features: Basidiospores 9-12 × 4.5-5.5 µm, from ellipsoid to fusiform, very irregular in size and shape, slightly verrucose, brown, some of them with a big droplet. Cheilocystidia 23-38 × 14-24 µm, from clavate to globose.

After the cheilocystidia were observed, species having these cells such as *C. cystidiocatenatus* (Gasparini 2007),

Fig. 1. *Amanita muscaria* var. *inzengae*

Fig. 2. *Cortinarius assiduus* var. *plesiocistus*

Fig. 3. *Cortinarius cystidifer*

Fig. 4. *Terfezia olbiensis*

C. cystidiophorus (Remaux in Bidaud 1993; Bidaud *et al.* 2008) and *C. cystiorapaceus* (Moser & Horak 1975; Peintner *et al.* 2002), were compared and ruled out. On the other hand, several species with fusoid basidiospores, according to Jacobsson & Soop (2000), Fernández Sasía (2003) and Moreno *et al.* (2004), are also quite different from *C. cystidifer*.

As a conclusion, the irregular size and shape of the basidiospores and the globose cheilocystidia are valuable tools for the identification of this species.

Cortinarius scobinaceus Malençon & Bertault var. *cistohelvelloides* (Bon) A.Ortega & Esteve-Rav. (= *C. cistohelvelloides* Bon)

Site 1. MTH 785; MTH 788; MTH 800. Site 2. MTH 786. Site 3. MTH 778. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features from MTH 778 collection: Pileus 130-240 mm in diameter, campanulate, becoming convex to planoconvex at maturity, hygrophanous, slightly striated at the margin and mammiform, from snuff brown to cigar brown at the mammiform area. Lamellae slightly ventricose and thick, with sinuate insertion, cinnamom. Stipe 16-26 × 2-4 mm, cylindrical,

sinuous, cinnamom with the lower half part with plenty of the universal veil in white color, which becomes a small ring in the middle area, where numerous brown spores can be observed.

Micromorphological features from MTH 778 collection: Basidia 28-32 × 7-8 μm, clavate, 4-spored. Basidiospores 8-11 × 4.5-5 μm, from ellipsoid to amygdaloid, verrucose, brown with a big droplet.

More information on this new variety can be found in Ortega *et al.* (2006). It is not the first time this species is collected in this area in Portugal; a previous collection in 1999 is reported in Ortega & Esteve-Raventós (2007). It seems to be the most abundant species of *Cortinarius* associated with *Cistus* spp.

Entoloma cistophilum Trimbach

Site 3. MTH 781. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 6-25 mm in diameter, convex to planoconvex at maturity, translucently striate, slightly mammiform, brownish grey to cigar brown at the mammiform area, showing a concentric band close to the margin when dry. Lamellae ventricose, greyish pink, moderately distant with sinuate insertion, lamellulae

present. Stipe 35-53 × 2-3 mm, cylindrical, broadened at the base, concolorous with pileus except at the basal part, where it shows a greyish white colour.

Micromorphological features: Basidiospores 7-9 × 6-8 µm, sub-isodiametrical, more or less pentagonal shaped, with a large guttule inside.

The spore dimensions and shape allowed us to differentiate this species from *E. hebes* and *E. plebejum*, which sometimes are also present beneath *Cistus* spp. Further information can be found in Noordeloos (1992).

Galerina vittiformis (Fr.) Earle

Site 3. MTH 777. Scattered, on moss, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 7-12 mm in diameter, conical, becoming convex at maturity, hygrophanous, striated and mammiform, from rust to dark yellow, lighter between striae. Lamellae ventricose, adnate, rather distant and a little darker than the pileus. Stipe 35-35 × 0.8-1.3 mm, cylindrical, brownish yellow at the apex, swollen at the base, where it turns brown.

Hebeloma mesophaeum (Pers.) Quéf.

Site 2. MTH 773. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Only one basidiocarp.

Inocybe flocculosa (Berk.) Sacc.

Site 2. MTH 787. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

This species is well known in different continents; according to Heim (1931) it was cited at that time in France, Finland, Denmark, England and America. As our collection was deteriorated by *Ceratophysella tergilobata*, it will be difficult to preserve it. An interesting work about the interrelation between *Ceratophysella* spp. and *Basidiomycetes* can be found in Mateos *et al.* (1996).

Laccaria laccata (Scop.) Cooke var. ***palidifolia*** (Peck) Peck

Site 1. MTH 801. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 12-30 mm in diameter, hemispherical, becoming plano-convex at maturity, hygrophanous, translucently striated at the margin, with central shallow depression, cream. Lamellae pale rose. Stipe 15-45 × 2-4 mm, cylindrical, sinuous, broadened at the apical area, concolorous with pileus.

Spores less ellipsoid and more globose than those of *L. laccata* var. *laccata* is the most important difference between these two varieties.

On the other hand, the 4-spored basidia is an important taxonomical feature to differentiate this species from the 2-spored one *L. tortilis*.

Laccaria proxima (Boud.) Pat.

Site 3. MTH 783; MTH 784. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 20-39 mm in diameter in the first collection, 15-22 mm in diameter in the second one, in which only 2 basidiocarps were collected; at first convex, flat-convex with central shallow depression at maturity, hygrophanous, reddish brown, margin pectinated. Lamellae distant, from adnate to

decurrent, with tooth, pinkish brown, lamellulae present. Stipe 46-68 × 5-19 mm in the first collection and 37-46 × 4-6 mm in the second one, concolorous with pileus, fibrillose, cylindrical, sinuous, compressed or twisted, broadened and white at the base.

Micromorphological features from the first collection: Basidiospores 9.5-11 × 7.5-9 µm, or 12-12.5 × 8-9 µm, ellipsoid, spiny. There is a considerable difference in the size of the basidiospores; such a difference as been reported in several works: (Moser 2000) 7.5-10 (-11) × 6.7-7.5 µm, (Kühner & Romagnesi 1978) 7-9.5 × 6-7.5 µm, (Malençon & Bertault 1975) 8.8-10.3 × 6.3-7.5 µm or 9.5-10.7 × 7.4-8.2 µm or 10.7-12.2 × 8-8.5 µm or 10.8-14 × 7.2-9.4 µm, where a macrosporal form was described and illustrated, (Phillips 1981) 7-9.5 × 6-7.5 µm, (Bas *et al.* 1995) 7.5-11 × 6-9 µm, (Vila & Llimona 2006) 10.7-12.5 × 7.7-9.3 µm, under the name of *Laccaria proxima* (Boud.) Pat. f. *mediterranea* Contu *nom. prov.* following the proposal of Contu (2004). At the moment we know that *L. proxima* collected beneath *Cistus* sp. in Morocco, Italy, Catalonia and Portugal show spores with the largest dimensions; further studies should be carried out in order to find out whether this is a new variety.

Lycoperdon perlatum Pers.

Site 3. MTH 769. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Omphalina sp.

Site 2. MTH 799. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 4-8 mm in diameter, with umbilicate centre, hygrophanous, translucently striated, from brownish cream to greyish cream, brown at the umbilicate area. Lamellae decurrent, distant, lamellulae present, white-cream. Stipe 9-14 × 0.5-1 mm, cylindrical, brown.

Micromorphological features: Basidiospores 6-9 × 4-6 µm, ellipsoid, hyaline with small oil droplets.

Cystidia and clamp connections absent.

Rickenella fibula (Bull.) Raithehl.

Site 3. MTH 766. Scattered, on moss, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 3-7 mm in diameter, at first plano-convex, infundibuliform at maturity, margin pectinate, pale orange-yellow to orange-red. Thick lamellae, decurrent, cream. Stipe 18-24 × 0.9-1 mm, cylindrical and concolorous with pileus.

Order ***Boletales***

Astraeus hygrometricus (Pers.) Morgan

Site 1. MTH 772. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Leccinum corsicum (Rolland) Singer

Site 2. MTH 791. Beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 31-55 mm in diameter, convex, brown. Pores circular, polygonal at maturity, 1-2 per mm, yellow. Tubes up to 12 mm long,

concolorous with pores, brownish at maturity. Stipe 35-55 × 15-27 mm, fusiform, light yellow and ornamented with granulations in yellowish brown colour.

This species was referred to as specific or typical *Cistus* mycobiont in Comandini *et al.* (2006).

Pisolithus arbizus (Scop.) Rauschert

Site 3. MTH 767. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Order *Russulales*

Lactarius cistophilus Bon & Timbach

Site 1. MTH 793; Site 2. MTH 794. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features from MTH 793 collection: Pileus 38-69 mm in diameter, at first convex, becoming expanded and later depressed, broadly lobed, viscid with some leaves stuck on the more or less separable cuticle, brownish cream, lighter at the border which shows lilac tinges in the young basidiocarps. Lamellae narrow, closely spaced, from adnate to slightly decurrent, cream, lamellulae present. Latex copious, white, becoming lilac on the flesh and lamellae. Stipe 15-52 × 8-16 mm, cylindrical, attenuated at the base, cream with brownish lilac areas. Although this species forms ectomycorrhizae with other *Cistus* spp., such as *C. albidus*, *C. laurifolius*, *C. monspeliensis*, *C. populifolius* or *C. salviifolius*, it is not so frequent as it is with *C. ladanifer*.

Lactarius tesquorum Malençon

Site 1. MTH 795; Site 2. MTH 796. Scattered on soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Macromorphological features from MTH 795 collection: Pileus 60-68 mm in diameter, at first convex, later flattened and then umbilicated. Cuticle not separable, from salmon cream to yellowish cream, covered with flecks, more abundant at the border area. Lamellae narrow, closely spaced, from adnate to slightly decurrent, cream salmon to cream, lamellulae present. Latex copious, white, with very hot taste. Stipe 17-30 × 11-14 mm, cylindrical, attenuated at the base, sometimes with shallow spot-like depressions, concolorous with pileus.

Russula cistoadelpha M.M. Moser & Trimbach

Site 2. MTH 774. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Only one basidiocarp. There is a comparative work on *cistophilus* *Russula* spp. in (Torrejón 2007).

Russula subfoetens Wm.G. Sm.

Site 2. MTH 797. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

Only two basidiocarps.

Macromorphological features: Pileus 31-34 mm in diameter, slightly viscid, flat convex to slightly depress, striated at margin, brown, dark brown at the depressed area. Lamellae cream sometimes bifurcate from Y insertion close to the stipe, lamellulae present. Stipe 33-40 × 9-10 mm, cylindrical, attenuated at the base, white. Flesh with the typical smell of the subsection *foentinae*.

Micromorphological features: Basidiospores 8.5-9 × 6-7 μm, with conical, verrucose and amyloid ornamentation.

Although this collection shows smaller basidiocarps than usually, micromorphological features are the typical ones. We have previously collected this species in Spain, in Portugal and in the south of Europe and as it is reported in Mastard (2004) this species is present in the Nordic countries as well.

Stereum hirsutum (Willd.) Pers.

Site 1. MTH 771. On wood of *Cistus ladanifer*.

Very small collection.

Order *Thelephorales*

Thelephora terrestris Ehrh.

Site 3. MTH 768. On soil, beneath *Cistus ladanifer*.

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